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VALIDATED FOR THE ESTIMATION OF AMLODIPINE IN HUMAN PLASMA OVER

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ABSTRACT

The present study aims to develop the bio-analytical method for the estimation of amlodipine in human plasma and evaluate the pharmacokinetic variables after a single oral dose in eight healthy male human volunteers in a two way, two period, and complete crossover design. For the estimation of the drugs present in the biological fluid, LC-MS/MS method is considered to be more suitable. The limit of quantification was 0.1 ng/ml for plasma amlodipine analysis. The geometric mean and the 90% confidence interval (CI) test/reference ratios were 101.2 (92.9-110.2%) for AUC_{last}, 99.6 (91.5-108.4%) for AUC_{0-inf} and 98.5 (89.0-109.1%) for C_{max}. Since the 90% CI for AUC_{last}, AUC_{0-inf} and C_{max} ratios were within in the 80-125% interval proposed by the US FDA, it was concluded that Amlodipine[®] 10 mg tablet (test formulation) was bioequivalent to Norvasc[®] 10 mg tablet, in terms of both rate and extent of absorption.

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INTRODUCTION

Mathematical analysis of plasma level vs. time curves permit estimations of half-lives, absorption and excretion rates, extent of absorption (area under the curve), and other constants that are useful in describing the fate of a given drug in an organism. Comparative bioavailability studies permit judgements as to the bioequivalence of drugs. It is now recognized that formulation factors can influence the biological availability of a medicament from a dosage unit in mammalian systems. Consequently, it has become common practice to establish bioavailability by measurement of blood levels of drugs following administration of dosage forms.

It should be noted that neither bioavailability nor bioequivalence data could be generated without analytic methodology to accurately measure drugs in biological fluids. Problems related to bioavailability and bioequivalence, new drug development, drug abuse, clinical pharmacokinetics, and drug research is highly dependent on accurately measured drugs in biological fluids. For the estimation of the drugs present in the biological fluid, LC-MS/MS method is considered to be more suitable since this is a powerful and rugged method. It is also extremely specific, linear, precise, accurate, sensitive and rapid.

MATERIALS AND INSTRUMENTS

Chemicals and reagents used

Acetonitrile, Methanol of HPLC grade, and Formic acid AR grade by Ranbaxy Fine Chemicals, Water HPLC grade from Milli-Q RO system, Ammonium acetate buffer Solution, Ammonia, Amlodipine.

Instruments used

Sartorius single pan digital balance (CP 323 S), ELC0 LI-610 pH meter. Waters UPLC with waters Micromass, Quattro premier mass spectrometer (LC-MS/MS) system with the configurations of binary solvent manager (pump), Sample manager (auto injector), Column oven, Triple state quadrupole analyzer, Photo multiplier detector System, MassLynx software version 4.0, Sonicator, Solid phase extractor.

METHODOLOGY

Validation of the method

Validation is a process which involves confirmation or establishment by laboratory studies that a method / procedure / system / analyst can give the required accuracy, precision, sensitivity, ruggedness, etc. In the most basic form, validation of an analytical procedure demonstrates that the procedure developed is suitable for its intended purpose. Validation of the method was carried out after the development of the LC-MS/MS method. This section describes the procedure followed for the validation of the methods developed.

Accuracy: Accuracy of the method was determined by relative and absolute recovery experiments. The relative recovery of the drug was calculated by comparing the concentration obtained from the drug supplemented plasma to the actually added concentration. To drug supplemented plasma, standard Amlodipine solution (three levels) and internal standard (Ondansetron hydrochloride dihydrate) solution were added. The preparation of solution was carried out adopting the procedure used for the preparation of the sample solution. The resulting sample solution was analyzed and the response factor was calculated.

The absolute recovery of Amlodipine was determined by comparing the response factor of the drug obtained from the plasma with response factor obtained by the direct injection of Amlodipine in mobile phase at three different levels. Recovery studies were carried out for three levels at six times and the % recovery, mean, standard deviation and % CV was calculated.

Precision: The precision of the method was determined by intraday precision and interday precision. The intraday precision was evaluated by analysis of plasma samples containing Amlodipine at three different concentrations containing internal standard using nine replicate determinations for three occasions. The interday precision was similarly evaluated over two-week period. Precision studies were carried out for three levels at nine times and three occasions. The mean

concentration, mean % bias, standard deviation and % CV were calculated.

Selectivity: The six blank plasma samples obtained from six different volunteers were analyzed and the chromatograms were recorded. These chromatograms were compared with the chromatograms obtained from standard solutions. Each chromatogram was tested for interference. The combination of the sample preparation procedure and chromatography provided an assay, which must be free from significant interfering endogenous plasma components at the retention times of Amlodipine and the internal standard.

Linearity and range/calibration curve: The different concentrations of standard solutions were prepared to contain 0.2 ng/ml to 20.0 ng/ml of Amlodipine containing 25.0 ng/ml of internal standard. These solutions were analyzed and the peak areas and response factors were calculated. The calibration curve was plotted using response factor Vs concentration of the standard solutions. The calibration curve was constructed on six different days over a two weeks period to determine the variability of the slopes and intercepts.

Sensitivity: Sensitivity of the method was determined by the lowest amount of amlodipine that can be quantitatively determined with suitable precision and accuracy.

System Suitability: Calculating the chromatographic parameters namely, column efficiency, resolution, peak asymmetry factor and capacity factor on the repetitive injection of standard solutions using the following formula performed system suitability of the methods.

Capacity factor (k') is a measure of how well the sample a column retains molecule during an isocratic separation. The ideal value of (k') ranges from 2-10.

$$\text{Capacity Factor } (k') = V_1 - V_0 / V_0$$

Where, V_1 is the retention volume at the apex of the peak (solute) and V_0 is the void volume of the system.

Resolution (R_s) is the difference between the retention times of two solutes divided by their average peak width. The ideal value of (R_s) is 1.5.

$$\text{Resolution } (R_s) = (R_{t1} - R_{t2}) / 0.5 (W_1 + W_2)$$

Where, R_{t1} and R_{t2} are the retention times of components 1 and 2. W_1 and W_2 are peak widths of components 1 and 2, respectively.

Selectivity (α) is a measure of relative retention of two components in a mixture. The ideal value of α is 2.

$$\text{Selectivity } (\alpha) = V_2 - V_0 / V_1 - V_0$$

Where, V_0 is the void volume of the column and V_2 & V_1 are the retention volumes of the second and first peaks, respectively.

Efficiency (N) of a column is measured by the number of theoretical plates per meter. Column with N ranging from 5,000 to 100,000 plates/meter are ideal for a good separation.

$$\text{Column efficiency } (N) = 16 R_t^2 / w^2$$

Where, R_t is the retention time and w is the peak width.

Peak Asymmetry Factor can be used as a criterion of column performance. For a well-packed column, an asymmetry factor of 0.9 to 1.1 should be achievable.

$$\text{Peak asymmetry factor } (A_s) = b/a$$

Where, a and b are the distances on either side of the peak mid point.

Limit of detection

Testing method: By LC-MS/MS In-house method
Based on Signal- to- Noise (3:1) approach
Determination of the signal-to-noise ratio is performed by

Limit of quantitation

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Determination of the signal- to- noise ratio is performed by comparing measured signals from samples with known low concentrations of Amlodipine with those of blank samples (i.e. mobile phase) and establishing the minimum concentration at which the Amlodipine can be reliably quantified.

Robustness of the method

For demonstrating the robustness of the method, slight variations in the optimized conditions were made and the standard solution was injected. The variation made were,

- ± 1 % in the ratio of methanol in the mobile phase,
- ± 0.5 unit in the pH of the buffer, and
- ± 0.05 ml of the flow rate.

Then the separation factor, retention times and peak asymmetry were calculated.

Recovery

The extraction efficiency of an analytical process, reported as a percentage of the known amount of the amlodipine carried through the amlodipine extraction and processing steps of the method.

Stability

Drug and internal standard stability is a biological matrix is a function of the storage condition, the chemical properties of the drug, the matrix and the container system. Stability procedures should evaluate the stability of the amlodipine for the duration of sample collection and handling, short-term storage (bench top, room temperature), long-term storage (frozen at the intended storage temperature), doing through the free and thaw cycles and after the analytical process.

Matrix effect

The direct or indirect alteration or interference in response due to the presence of unintended sample for analysis or other interfering substances in the sample.

Anticoagulet effect

An anticoagulant is a substance that steps blood from clotting, the anticoagulants commonly used are Heparin, Citrate- Phosphate–dextrose (CPD), EDTA. Anticoagulant effect is performed to check the effect of different anticoagulants on analytical results.

Blood collection

Volunteers were given serial numbers and were allocated to the treatment. All the volunteers were assembled in Bioequivalence Centre, Centre for Clinical Trials, Adyar Hospital, Chennai. After

overnight fasting of 12 hrs, their pulse rates, BP were recorded and a sterile intravenous catheter was introduced with strict aseptic precautions for blood collection. A total of 21 blood samples were collected at 0 hr (before drug administration) 0.0, 1.0, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 7.0, 8.0, 9.0, 10.0, 11.0, 12.0, 14.0, 16.0, 24.0, 48.0, 72.0, 96.0 and 120.0 hrs post dosing. Through I.V. Cannula, blood samples (5ml) were collected via disposable syringes in pre-citrated centrifugal tubes. The withdrawn samples were centrifuged at 3500 rpm for 10 minutes to separate plasma. They were transferred into airtight containers and stored at deep freeze condition.

Evaluation

The evaluations of the results were done after tabulation of the data and respective graphical representation. The conclusion of the study was made.

Quality assurance

The analysis was carried out in a GLP regulated environment and was conducted in compliance with the principles of Good Laboratory Practice. All the analytical instruments used for the study were calibrated & validated and the analytical methods adopted were validated as per the latest guidelines in force.

Estimation of amlodipine in plasma

A Waters UPLC with Waters Micromass Quattro premier Mass spectrometer (LC-MS/MS) system was used for the analysis.

PREPARATION OF SOLUTIONS FOR ESTIMATION

Amlodipine standard solutions (spiking solutions)

The following concentrations of Amlodipine in methanol: water-50: 50 for Calibration Curve - 4.0, 8.0, 20.0, 40.0, 80.0, 160.0, 240.0, 320.0, 400.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and for Quality Control - 12.0, 120.0, 280.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ were prepared.

Internal standard solution

Ondansetron Hydrochloride dihydrate equivalent to 10mg of Ondansetron weighed and transferred into a 100ml volumetric flask, to which about 70ml of Methanol was added, and was sonicated

to dissolve the material completely and volume made up with Methanol and was vortexed. From the above solution 0.1ml was pipetted into a 10ml volumetric flask and volume made up with methanol to get 1µg/mL concentration. From this solution, 1.25ml solution was pipetted into a 50ml volumetric flask and volume made up with water to get 25ng/ml concentration

Procedure for preparation of Bulk standard plasma

The bulk standard plasma samples were stored at -80°C until analysis and thawed to room temperature before use. The above table shows that from the standard solutions, 10.0ml of bulk plasma calibration curve samples containing the drug were prepared to give final concentration of 0.2, 0.4, 1.0, 2.0, 4.0, 8.0, 12.0, 16.0, 20.0 µg/ml of Amlodipine in plasma. And 10.0ml of bulk plasma quality control samples were prepared to contain 0.6(LQC), 6.0(MQC), 14.0(HQC) µg/ml of Amlodipine in plasma.

Table 1: preparation of Bulk standard plasma

S No.	Spiking solution (Standard solutions) µg/ml	Volume of spiking solution to be taken, µl	Volume of plasma to be taken, ml	Final concentration ng/ml
1	4	500	9.500	0.2
2	8	500	9.500	0.4
3	20	500	9.500	1
4	40	500	9.500	2
5	80	500	9.500	4
6	160	500	9.500	8
7	240	500	9.500	12
8	320	500	9.500	16
9	400	500	9.500	20
LQC	12	500	9.500	0.6
MQC	120	500	9.500	6
HQC	280	500	9.500	14

EXTRACTION PROCEDURE (SOLID PHASE EXTRACTION)

50µl of Internal standard solution was admixed with 1.0ml of sample in a vial and vortexed for 1min. Oasis HLB Extraction cartridges were placed on vacuum manifold vacuum was set to 5 Hg pressure. Adding 1ml methanol to each cartridge and draining it out by applying vacuum conditioned the cartridges. Equilibration was done by adding 2ml water to each cartridge and draining it out by applying vacuum. 1.0ml of pre-mixed sample was loaded to each cartridge and drained out by applying vacuum. Each cartridge was first washed with 1ml of 0.1% Ammonia in water and then washed with 1ml of 5% methanol. The vacuum was released, manifold cover removed and waste fluids were discarded. Elution was done by adding 0.8ml of 0.1% Ammonia in methanol solution the eluates were collected in suitable vessels and injected into the system.

ESTIMATION OF AMLODIPINE BY LC-MS/MS METHOD

Estimation of plasma samples from the volunteers was carried out using the optimized chromatographic conditions. The standard and sample solutions were injected and chromatograms were recorded. The typical scans and chromatograms of the standard and sample solutions.

The calibration curves were constructed routinely for spiked plasma containing Amlodipine and internal standard during process of pre-study validation and in-study validation. The mobile phase used for the estimation provided a well-defined separation between the drug, internal standard and endogenous components. The zero hours (pre-dose) samples of all subjects showed no interference at the retention time of both the

Amlodipine and internal standard. The response factor of the standard and sample solutions was calculated. The concentration of Amlodipine present in plasma samples were calculated.

BIOAVAILABILITY STUDY OF AMLODIPINE

Pharmacokinetics data

Pharmacokinetic parameters such as Peak plasma concentration (C_{max}), Time to peak Concentration (t_{max}), Area under the plasma concentration - time curve (AUC_{0-t} & $AUC_{0-\infty}$), elimination rate constant (k_{eli}), Elimination half-life ($t_{1/2}$) were calculated separately and the blood level data of the Test product and Reference product was measured. The observations are given in **Table 17**.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validation of the developed methods

The real goal of validation process is to challenge the method and determine limits of allowed variability for the conditions needed to run the method. This section deals with the discussions of the results obtained.

Recovery studies

Recovery for amlodipine and internal standard is performed by comparing the analytical results area of extracted samples at three different concentrations of LQC, MQC and HQC with unextracted standards results area that represents recovery of the amlodipine and internal standard. Recovery studies were carried out for three levels at five replicates and the %recovery, mean, standard deviation and %CV was calculated (Amlodipine & Internal standard). An analysis of the results shows that the % CV of amlodipine and internal standard recovery values are less than 15.00% thus establishing that the developed method is accurate and reliable.

Accuracy

Accuracy of the method was determined by relative and absolute recovery experiments. The absolute recovery of Amlodipine was determined by comparing the response factor of the drug obtained from the plasma with response factor

obtained by the direct injection of Amlodipine in mobile phase at three different levels. Recovery studies were carried out for three levels at six times and the % recovery, mean, standard deviation and % CV was calculated. An analysis of the results shows that the % CV of absolute and the relative recovery values are less than 15.00% thus establishing that the developed method is accurate and reliable.

Precision

The precision of the method was determined by intraday precision and interday precision studies. The intraday precision was evaluated by analysis of blank plasma sample containing Amlodipine at three different concentrations of LQC, MQC and HQC using nine replicate determinations for three occasions. The interday precision was similarly evaluated over two-week period. The mean concentration, Mean % bias, standard deviation and % CV were calculated. The results of the precision studies reveal that the developed method is precise.

Selectivity

The six blank plasma samples obtained from six different volunteers were analyzed and the chromatograms were recorded. These chromatograms were compared with the chromatograms obtained from standard solutions. Each chromatogram was tested for interference. The combination of the sample preparation procedure and chromatography provided an assay, which is free from significant interfering endogenous plasma components at the retention times of Amlodipine and the internal standard. Endogenous interferences were not detected at the retention time of Amlodipine and internal standard.

Linearity and range

The different concentrations of standard solutions were prepared to contain 0.2 to 20.0 ng /ml of Amlodipine and 25.0 ng/ml of internal standard. These solutions were analyzed and the peak areas and response factors were calculated. The calibration curve was plotted using response factor Vs concentration of the standard solutions. The Standard curve fitting is determined by applying the simplest model that adequately

describes the concentration-response relationship using appropriate weighting and statistical tests for goodness of fit. The calibration curve was constructed on six different days over a two weeks period to determine the variability of the slopes and intercepts. The lowest standard on the calibration curve was 0.2 ng/ml. The results indicated little inter-day variability of slopes and intercepts, as well as good linearity ($r^2 > 0.99$) over the concentration range studied, which indicates good precision and linearity of the method.

System suitability studies

The parameters namely column efficiency, resolution, peak asymmetry factor and capacity factor for the standard solutions were calculated on repetitive injection of standard solutions. The values obtained demonstrated the suitability of the system for the analysis of the Amlodipine in plasma.

Limit of detection

Testing method: By LC-MS/MS In-house method
Based on Signal-to-Noise (3:1) approach
Limit of detection is 0.1 ng/ml.

Determination of the signal-to-noise ratio is performed by comparing measured signals from samples with known low concentrations of Amlodipine with those of blank samples (i.e. mobile phase) and establishing the minimum concentration at which the Amlodipine can be reliably detected.

Limit of quantitation

Testing method: By LC-MS/MS In-house method
Based on Signal to Noise (10: 1) approach
Limit of quantitation is 0.2 ng/ml.

Determination of the signal-to-noise ratio is performed by comparing measured signals from samples with known low concentrations of Amlodipine with those of blank samples (i.e. mobile phase) and establishing the minimum concentration at which the Amlodipine can be reliably quantified. The data show that the developed methods have adequate sensitivity. The LOD and LOQ values determined, however, these values are affected by the separation conditions

namely, column, reagents, instrumentation and data systems. Instrumental changes, particularly pumping systems and detectors and use of the contaminated reagents or grades other than HPLC grade solvent, can result in large changes in S/N ratio due to baseline noise and drift.

Robustness of the method

For demonstrating the robustness of the method, slight variations in the optimized conditions were made and the standard solution was injected. The variations made were, $\pm 1\%$ in the ratio of methanol in the mobile phase, 0.05 ml of the flow rate. Then the separation factor, retention times and peak asymmetry were calculated.

Stability studies: Stock solution stability

Height calibration standard of amlodipine and internal standard stock solutions were prepared and appropriately diluted to determine initial areas, after 8 hours at room temperature and for 1 day at 2-8°C. The next day areas of stability samples and freshly prepared samples were compared to determine % change over stability of two days period. The results indicated for stock solution of amlodipine and internal standard stable at room temperature for 24 hrs and 2-8°C for 48 hrs.

Bench top stability

Bench top stability of amlodipine in matrix is determined at LQC and HQC levels. Freshly prepared five replicates of samples were kept at room temperature for 24 hrs. After processed and analyzed along with calibration samples concentration was calculated to determine by % change. It was found to be stable in matrix for at least 30 hrs at room temperature with % change of 10.01% and 11% at LQC and HQC samples 5 respectively.

Freeze and thaw stability

Freeze and thaw stability of amlodipine was determined after three freeze and thaw cycles at LQC and HQC levels. Stability in matrix after 2 freeze and thaw cycle at -70°C. Concentrations were calculated to determine mean % change of after 2 cycles for LQC and HQC was found 8.01 and 4.01, respectively.

Long-term stability

Stability at -70°C was determined by freezing five aliquots each of the LQC, MQC and HQC of amlodipine samples under the same conditions as that of the study samples. The storage time in a long term stability evaluation should exceed the time between the date of first sample collection and the date of last sample analysis. Concentrations were calculated to determine % change after 40 days for LQC, MQC and HQC was found 9.01, 10.08 and 10.05 respectively.

Anticoagulant effect

Anticoagulant effect is performed to check the effect of different anticoagulant on analytical results. Process and analyze using buffered plasma and five aliquots of each LQC, MQC and HQC samples. Calculate mean, standard deviation, % nominal concentration of calculated mean and % coefficient of variation for samples. Precision and accuracy of batch % C.V and Nominal concentration with in limits of 15% and $85 \pm 115\%$ respectively.

Matrix effect

Matrix effect should be measured in six different lots of same matrix to ensure that precision, selectivity and sensitivity is not effected by different lots of matrix. Process and analyze three sets of LQC and HQC samples using six different lot of matrix. Calculated %Bias was found to be LQC and HQC 2.35%, 3.95% respectively. Oral administration of the Test product and Reference product in the fasting state exhibited Measurable Amlodipine blood levels in all the volunteers from

0.50 hr onwards. Measurable Amlodipine blood levels were noticed in all subjects up to 120.00 hrs.

The mean peak plasma concentration i.e. C_{max} for Amlodipine after administration of the Test and Reference product was 3.447 ± 1.124 and 3.467 ± 1.374 ng /ml, respectively. The time to peak concentration i.e. T_{max} for Amlodipine after administration of the Test and Reference product was 7.250 ± 2.5 and 6.625 ± 1.5 hrs, respectively.

The area under the plasma concentration-time curve i.e. AUC_{0-120} for Amlodipine after administration of the Test and Reference product was 164.683 ± 74.633 and 164.303 ± 77.496 ng.h/ml, respectively. The elimination rate constant (k_{el}) for Amlodipine after administration of the Test and Reference product was 0.020 ± 0.001 and $0.020 \pm 0.001 \text{ h}^{-1}$, respectively. The elimination half-life ($t_{1/2}$) for Amlodipine after administration of the Test and Reference product was 34.74 ± 4.63 and 35.78 ± 3.18 hrs. The area under the plasma concentration-time curve for infinitive time ($AUC_{0-\infty}$) for Amlodipine after administration of the Test and Reference product was 177.92 ± 72.87 and 177.93 ± 78.54 ng.h/ml respectively.

The limit of quantification was 0.1 ng/ml for plasma amlodipine analysis. The geometric mean and the 90% confidence interval (CI) test/reference ratios were 101.2 (92.9-110.2%) for AUC_{last} , 99.6 (91.5-108.4%) for $AUC_{0-\text{inf}}$ and 98.5 (89.0-109.1%) for C_{max} .

Table 2: Plasma Concentration (ng/ml) Data of the Test Product.

Time	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	Mean	S.D
0.0	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
1.0	0.076	0.491	1.343	0.183	0.804	1.039	0.666	0.647	0.657	0.418
2.0	0.334	0.877	0.589	0.670	1.542	1.584	1.851	1.371	1.102	0.554
3.0	0.716	1.187	1.021	1.170	1.997	1.985	1.958	2.081	1.514	0.545
4.0	1.174	1.959	1.040	1.317	2.140	2.135	2.190	2.250	1.776	0.508
5.0	2.405	4.435	2.644	1.935	2.889	2.770	3.883	3.230	3.024	0.808
6.0	2.284	2.607	2.813	1.903	2.997	3.155	4.170	3.824	2.969	0.753
7.0	2.308	2.579	3.417	1.790	3.006	3.332	4.424	4.009	3.108	0.875
8.0	2.315	2.421	2.909	1.877	3.146	3.550	3.813	3.882	2.989	0.740
9.0	1.842	2.095	2.836	2.187	2.612	3.185	3.686	3.638	2.760	0.702
10.0	1.802	2.136	2.781	1.814	2.557	3.826	3.601	3.394	2.614	0.675

11.0	1.793	2.035	2.706	2.019	2.413	2.798	3.534	3.480	2.597	0.659
12.0	1.607	2.008	2.695	1.540	2.066	2.689	3.607	3.247	2.432	0.753
14.0	1.531	1.964	2.576	1.549	1.847	2.368	3.560	3.023	2.302	0.724
16.0	1.465	1.921	2.439	1.379	1.748	2.314	3.378	2.865	2.189	0.696
24.0	1.387	1.856	2.448	1.284	1.563	1.987	3.357	2.799	2.085	0.729
48.0	1.109	1.754	1.140	0.943	1.524	1.751	1.937	2.187	1.543	0.442
72.0	0.706	1.112	0.755	0.413	0.751	1.640	1.553	1.635	1.071	0.485
96.0	0.358	0.946	0.692	0.235	0.638	0.979	1.005	1.339	0.774	0.365
120.0	0.264	0.022	0.477	0.116	0.344	0.761	0.666	1.072	0.465	0.352

Table 3: Plasma Concentration (ng/ml) Data of the Reference Product.

Time	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	MEAN	S.D.
0.0	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
1.0	0.245	0.642	0.863	0.694	0.632	1.152	1.238	0.663	0.766	0.317
2.0	0.788	1.174	0.909	0.807	1.465	1.622	2.575	1.440	1.348	0.589
3.0	0.970	1.525	1.109	1.212	1.874	2.017	2.777	1.997	1.685	0.601
4.0	1.183	2.047	1.162	1.503	2.098	2.200	2.562	2.095	1.856	0.511
5.0	2.315	4.848	2.675	1.809	2.586	2.680	3.658	2.933	2.948	0.919
6.0	2.136	2.293	2.792	2.100	2.796	3.216	3.925	3.652	2.864	0.689
7.0	2.097	2.135	3.342	1.868	2.992	3.579	4.524	3.893	3.054	0.956
8.0	2.164	2.596	2.813	1.825	3.004	3.713	3.991	3.727	2.979	0.783
9.0	1.821	2.643	2.798	1.770	2.568	3.346	3.866	3.651	2.808	0.780
10.0	1.809	2.049	2.728	1.715	2.438	3.128	3.624	3.159	2.581	0.696
11.0	1.658	2.144	2.810	1.760	2.361	3.095	3.581	3.095	2.563	0.691
12.0	1.490	1.987	2.661	1.618	1.916	3.004	3.568	3.084	2.416	0.766
14.0	1.430	2.026	2.541	1.690	1.809	2.657	3.490	3.096	2.342	0.724
16.0	1.412	1.966	2.421	1.594	1.741	2.421	3.367	2.935	2.232	0.681
24.0	1.356	1.785	2.340	1.176	1.489	1.997	3.311	2.597	2.006	0.716
48.0	1.028	1.689	1.325	0.943	1.422	1.836	2.132	2.064	1.555	0.449
72.0	0.718	0.715	0.896	0.490	0.671	1.508	1.781	1.567	1.043	0.495
96.0	0.321	0.620	0.721	0.268	0.603	1.393	1.088	1.355	0.796	0.436
120.0	0.208	0.312	0.329	0.118	0.478	0.934	0.700	0.973	0.507	0.327

Table 4: Mean Plasma Concentrations of Reference and Test Product (ng/ml)

Time (h)	Test Product		Reference Product	
	Mean	S.D	Mean	S.D
0.0	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
1.0	0.657	0.418	0.766	0.317
2.0	1.102	0.554	1.348	0.589
3.0	1.514	0.545	1.685	0.601
4.0	1.776	0.508	1.856	0.511
5.0	3.024	0.808	2.948	0.919
6.0	2.969	0.753	2.864	0.689
7.0	3.108	0.875	3.054	0.956
8.0	2.989	0.740	2.979	0.783
9.0	2.760	0.702	2.808	0.780
10.0	2.614	0.675	2.581	0.696

11.0	2.597	0.659	2.563	0.691
12.0	2.432	0.753	2.416	0.766
14.0	2.302	0.724	2.342	0.724
16.0	2.189	0.696	2.232	0.681
24.0	2.085	0.729	2.006	0.716
48.0	1.543	0.442	1.555	0.449
72.0	1.071	0.485	1.043	0.495
96.0	0.774	0.365	0.796	0.436
120.0	0.465	0.352	0.507	0.327

Table 5: Summary of Results (n=12)

S.No	PARAMETERS	TEST PRODUCT	REFERENCE PRODUCT	% RATIO
1.	AUC ₀₋₁₂₀ (ng.h/ml)	164.683	164.303	100.23
2.	AUC _{0-∞} (ng.h/ml)	177.92	177.93	99.99
3.	C _{max} (ng/ml)	3.447	3.467	99.42
4.	t _{max} (h)	7.250	6.625	109.43
5.	k _{eli} (h ⁻¹)	0.020	0.020	100.00
6.	t _{1/2} (h)	34.74	35.78	97.09

FIG. 1: PLASMA MQC OF AMLODIPINE AND INTERNAL STANDARD

FIG. 2: CALIBRATION CURVE FOR AMLODIPINE

Compound name: Amlodipine
 Correlation coefficient: $r = 0.999838$, $r^2 = 0.999676$
 Calibration curve: $0.0171835 * x + 0.00135536$
 Response type: Internal Std (Ref 2), Area * (IS Conc. / IS Area)
 Curve type: Linear, Origin: Exclude, Weighting: 1/x, Axis trans: None

Fig. 3: MEAN CONCENTRATION (ng/ml) v/s TIME (hours.) CURVE AT EVERY HOUR OF EACH VOLUNTEER

CONCLUSION

Based on the data presented in this report, it can be concluded that the present method is validated for the estimation of Amlodipine in human plasma over concentration range of 0.2 to 20.0 ng/ml. The precision and accuracy are very much within the prescribed limits in this concentration range. Expected recoveries were observed in the present processing technique for LQC, MQC and HQC. The values obtained from system suitability studies demonstrated the suitability of the system for the analysis of the Amlodipine in plasma. Limit of detection of the methods is 0.1 ng/ml and Limit of quantitation is 0.2 ng/ml that shows that

the developed method has adequate sensitivity and also more than 50 samples can be processed at a time without affecting the assay values.

Since the 90% CI for AUC_{last} , AUC_{0-inf} and C_{max} ratios were within in the 80-125% interval proposed by the US FDA, it was concluded that Amlodipine® 10 mg tablet (test formulation) was bioequivalent to Norvasc 10 mg tablet, in terms of both rate and extent of absorption.

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